

**Mixed Ligand Complexes of Uranium(VI)
with Sudan Violet and selected Ligands**

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THERE is no report in the literature about the analytical aspects of solution equilibria of 1,4-diaminoanthraquinone, (Sudan violet, hereinafter SV). In this paper we describe the pH-titrimetric behaviour of SV in acetone-water medium and the complexation equilibria of the binary and mixed ligand complexes of uranyl ion with this reagent.

o-Aminophenol (*o*-AP), picolinic acid (Pic), 8-hydroxyquinoline (8-HQ) or 2,2-bipyridyl (Bipy) were used as a secondary ligand. The study was undertaken to explore the potentialities of Sudan violet (SV) in ternary complex formation and the effect of the varying π -accepting capability of the secondary ligands on the stability of the ternary complexes of uranium(VI).

Experimental

Analytical grade reagents were used. A stock solution of 5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of U^{VI} was prepared

TABLE 1—ACIDITY CONSTANTS* OF THE LIGANDS AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY* AND MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES** OF UVI AND SOME RELATED DATA

$I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4), Temp. = $20 \pm 0.1^\circ$, Solvent : 50% (v/v) Acetone

Ligand	pK	$\log K_{UL}^U$	$\log K_{UL_2}^{UL}$	$\log \beta_{UL_2}^U$	$\log \beta_{U(SV)L}^U$	$\log K_{U(SV)L}^{U(SV)}$	$\log K_{UL(SV)}^{UL(SV)}$	$\Delta \log K_U$
SV	9.30 (H/H ₄ A)	8.01	4.50	12.51				
Pic	5.75 (HL/L)	3.87	4.25	8.12	13.82	5.22	9.95	+1.95
8-HQ	5.15 (H ₂ L ⁺ /HL)	4.10	4.35	8.45	12.95	4.95	8.85	+0.85
	10.05 (HL/L)							
Bipy	4.45 (LH ⁺ /H)	3.70	4.00	7.70	12.52	4.52	8.82	+0.82
<i>o</i> -AP	3.99 (H ₂ L ⁺ /HL)	3.95	4.10	8.05	12.01	4.02	8.05	+0.05
	9.45 (HL/L)							

*Constants accurate to ± 0.02 . **Constants accurate to ± 0.05 .

using uranyl nitrate (AnalaR). The uranium content was determined as recommended¹. Solution of 1,4-diaminoanthraquinone ($1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was prepared in pure acetone. Stock solutions ($10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ each) of *o*-AP, Pic, 8-HQ and Bipy were prepared by dissolving the ligands in acetone. Potassium hydroxide standard solution (0.1 mol dm^{-3}), sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid standard solutions were prepared using deionised water.

All measurements were performed in the presence of 50% (v/v) acetone at $20 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The measured pH values in acetone-water mixtures were corrected as described elsewhere². The ionic strength was kept constant at 100 mmol dm^{-3} (NaClO_4). All titrations were carried out using 35 mmol dm^{-3} KOH as titrant so that any possibility of the precipitation of KClO_4 ($K_{sp} = 1.1 \times 10^{-2}$) under the experimental conditions can be precluded.

Results and Discussion

The proton association constants for the free ligands and the stability constants for the binary and ternary complexes were calculated from the titration data using a corrected version of the computer programme SCOGS³.

The formation constants of the UO_2 -SV binary complexes were calculated taking into account the species H, H₄A, H₃A, UO_2 , $\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_3\text{A})$, $\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_3\text{A})_2$, where H₄A is the neutral form of SV. For the evaluation of formation constant of the ternary complexes, the species H, H₄A, H₃A, H₂L⁺, HL, L, UO_2 , UO_2L , UO_2L_2 , $\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_3\text{A})$, $\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_3\text{A})_2$, $\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_3\text{A})\text{HL}$, and $\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_3\text{A})\text{L}$ were considered, where H₂L⁺ = *o*-AP or 8-HQ. Results are presented in Table 1.

The stability of the ternary complexes were found to increase within the following series of ligands : *o*-AP < Bipy < 8-HQ < Pic. Ternary complexes containing ligands with heteroaromatic nitrogen are generally more stable than that containing *o*-AP as a second ligand⁴, hence $\Delta \log K$ has more positive value as compared to that of the *o*-AP complex. The formation of the UO_2^{2+} ternary complexes

containing heteroaromatic nitrogen ligands appears to be dependent on the ring size of the chelate which seems to offset in the increasing basicities of the secondary ligands. Picolinic acid acts as a bidentate ligand in which the ligating atoms are the oxygen of the carboxyl OH and the nitrogen of the heterocyclic ring⁵ and gives the most stable ternary chelate. This is partly due to an increasing better neutralisation of charge in the $\text{UO}_2(\text{SV})(\text{Pic})$ ternary complex compared with the $[\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_3\text{A})]^{2+}$ binary complex.

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